

SC6

Disruptive Technologies Supporting Labour Market Decision Making

Grant Agreement number: 870702

Deliverable D6.2

Website, Social Media, Logo

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Project Identity

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No 870702

Status, Abstract, Keywords, Statement of originality

Dissemination level:	Public
Contractual date of delivery:	31 Mar 2020
Actual date of delivery:	N/A
Work Package:	WP6 Communications
Type:	Website
Approval Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
Abstract This document provides details of the HECAT project website, social media sites and agreed logos	
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History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.1	11.03.2020	Creation of the initial document structure	Aisling Tuite
1.0	X	Final version	

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Website

The website domain is: **www.hecat.eu**

[HECAT HOME](#) [ABOUT](#) [WORK PACKAGES](#) [DELIVERABLES](#) [CONTACT](#) [BLOG](#)

Social Media

Social Media will be in the form of a Twitter account. The twitter account **@SoUnemployment (Unemployment Studies)** is a pre-existing account hosted by the project coordinators WIT with access to relevant consortium members within WIT.

Unemployment Studies
290 Tweets

Hecat
Disruptive Technologies Supporting
Labour Market Decision Making

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Unemployment Studies
@SoUnemployment Follows you

EU H2020 SC6 project HECAT- Disruptive Technologies Supporting Labour Market Decisions. Tweets by Ray Griffin

WUERC, WIT Waterford, Ireland wuerc.com Joined August 2015

530 Following 438 Followers

Followed by HECAT, Philip Finn, and 61 others you follow

Tweets Tweets & replies Media Likes

Logos

A number of logos have been chosen for the HECAT project

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Use of Website, Social Media & Logos

The use, purpose and access of the website, social media and logos will be set out in the HECAT Project Handbook and the HECAT Communications Handbook which will be distributed to all consortium members and will be available on the shared Google Drive repository